

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

Module B: AI, trust and awareness - Introduction & Literature review

D3.1 MOD. B, S1-2

September 2024

Funded by
the European Union

This document is part of the deliverable *KT4D Social Risk Toolkit - Modules A, B, and C (Version 1)* (2024) authored by Morisseau, T., & Lima, E., and accessible <https://zenodo.org/records/11491486>

Deliverable Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence in multiple aspects of our daily lives poses a great challenge in shaping civic participation within societies. Effective civic engagement finds its foundation in the empowerment of citizens who actively participate in public discourse, and in the articulation of their viewpoints. Understanding the dynamics that underpin trust in democratic institutions in this new context is thus important.

Module A questions individuals' capacity to navigate AI-based content and recommendations while safeguarding their autonomy and free will. Module B examines the requisites for the utilisation of AI to preserve institutional trust. Indeed, the use of AI in a wide range of fields could generate situations that are, or are perceived to be, unfair, thereby threatening the social balance established between members of the same community. Module C puts the new challenges posed by technological transformations into perspective, by analysing historical precedents and how they have shaped culture and social interactions over centuries.

Through a comprehensive exploration and assessment, modules A, B and C of KT4D's Social Risk Toolkit will seek to address an important challenge: identify exactly where regulation is needed to ensure that AI benefits society as a whole, and identify the conditions for trust in social institutions, in order to guarantee effective public debate and societal choices are made by citizens themselves.

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Module B: AI, trust and awareness

Introduction

AI represents a new challenge in the way we live together as a society. Because AI challenges our ability to think collectively about reality and to grasp a rich and diverse reality, serious thought needs to be given to the place we want AI to take in our lives. The way knowledge technologies are used also structure the informational landscape and play an important role in defining our public space.

In this module, we will examine the conditions of trust in the use of AI by companies and governments – making individuals vulnerable to strategies designed to change their behaviours. There is an imbalance of power between platforms, which have vast amounts of data about users (and can therefore manipulate the content they deliver), and users, who often have little understanding of how their data is used or how algorithms dictate the content they are fed (Lewandowsky & Pomerantsev, 2022). The aim of regulation must be to strengthen trust in institutions, a basic condition for the functioning of democracy. Proposals of ethics committees should be carefully examined in the light of the true point of view of the individuals, and the customs and habits of the societies in which they live. From this point of view, regulating the way social networks operate is particularly important. There is a duality in the influence of social media platforms on democratic systems: they provide both a very efficient forum for expression, but also undermine the trust placed in institutions that usually guarantee the reliability of information, as the origin of information becomes increasingly blurred.

Another aspect is the relationship between citizens themselves. The advent of Artificial Intelligence in everyday life has promoted modes of exchange and interactions, to which all sectors of society must adapt. The question we are exploring here in more depth concerns the nature of trust and distrust as applied to AI, both in the production of content (via tools such as ChatGPT or Midjourney), and in our very relationship with the world and with others.

We will attempt to answer these questions from a socio-cognitive angle, drawing on the literature on psychology of trust, and exploring (in the experimental component of this module) people's moral intuitions surrounding the integration of tools such as ChatGPT or Midjourney in professional settings. The first section focuses on the conditions of trust in the use of AI and big data by companies and governments, and how algorithms can undermine the conditions of public deliberation. The second section looks at the conditions under which the use of AI is acceptable to individuals in collaborative contexts, from a psychosocial perspective. We also examine the consequences of the mediation of our representations of the world by new knowledge technologies, and outline possible paths for preserving the capacity of different social groups to form rich and unique sensibilities.

State of the art: literature review

On the use of AI and big data by companies and governments

Trust in the use of AI to produce truthful information

For many scholars¹, the rise of digital communications and in particular social media is one of the main, if not the only, cause of a so-called "infodemia". Over the last decade, there has been a great deal of literature on the ease with which false information spreads, with some showing, for example, that "false information spreads six times faster than true information." (Vosoughi, Roy & Aral, 2018)² Misinformation is not a recent concern, nor is it a social media phenomenon. It was present before the digital age (Altay, Berriche & Acerbi, 2023), and one can easily find examples of misinformation disseminated by traditional media such as newspapers and television. The essayist Jonathan Swift observed in 1710 that "it often happens that, if a lie be believed only for an hour, it hath done its work, and there is no further occasion for it. Falsehood flies, and truth comes limping after it."

The evidence suggesting that fake news and deliberate misinformation significantly change people's opinions is not particularly strong. In the United States, while many individuals do consume fake news, these individuals are predominantly those with strong partisan leanings, who seek out fake news that confirms their preconceptions, viewing it more as a form of entertainment rather than a catalyst for changing their views. To date, **research indicates that the overall amount of fake news circulating on social networks is minimal, comprising only about 2-3% of the total information** (Altay, Berriche & Acerbi, 2023). **This small percentage is largely consumed by individuals with extreme political views that align with the fake news content.** Fake news represents a very small percentage of the information consumed in the US (0.15% according to Allen et al., 2021) and 80% of total exposure to fake news can be attributed to a very small number (1%) of individuals (Grinberg et al., 2019). Particularly in a democracy, the informational environment is largely demand-driven. The prevalence of particular types of content is primarily due to public interest rather than deliberate attempts to influence people. Journalists and editors do have some agency in selecting which stories to cover, and how to cover them, but the overwhelming selection bias of the population plays a significant role. Journalists aim to write content that will attract readership. Therefore, the presence of fake news is often a reflection of pre-existing public demand and agreement with the content.

However, recent advancements in artificial intelligence and large language models have sparked renewed discussions concerning misinformation. Should we be concerned about AI-based platforms convincing people of false information and deteriorating public discourse on important topics? These technological developments could indeed alter the public's ability to discern truth from falsehood. The proliferation of content generated by LLMs and other generative visual models—ranging from sophisticated propaganda to targeted marketing—is somewhat worrying. There is at least two ways

¹ "Post-truth" became the Oxford Dictionaries' Word of the Year in 2016.

² This famous study by Vosoughi et al. showed that a small number of fake news stories can be highly influential and reach between 1,000 and 100,000 people. Yet, these figures need to be balanced against the potential dissemination of true information in general (not just of rumours that have been proven to be true) and the latter is, in fact, much more widely and rapidly disseminated (Acerbi, 2019).

AI could lower the quality of information online, but they will probably have low consequences anyway.³

1. First, AI increases people's ability to produce a lot of text

Online content is often created with the intention of persuading individuals to accept particular points of view. Let's say a given AI system writes a massive number of articles, all arguing for some conclusion X. How can people trust the information that is being shared if an AI can produce any article in an instant? But there are also reasons to be optimistic.

First of all, there is already an enormous amount of information on the internet. And the bottleneck is not how many articles there are on a given topic, because there is already far more than anyone will ever read. The production stage is already relatively cheap. One could hire someone to write an article. It will only cost them a few thousand dollars at most. Even if propagandists are more inclined to use ChatGPT to produce fake news and take advantage of the cost reduction, it will make a very small difference because the cost of writing articles is not the main cost anyway.

Rather, **the bottleneck is individual attention. It is how to get people to read them and take them seriously.** That bottleneck is largely controlled by the big players in the field: cable news, big newspapers (and to a lesser extent peers and colleagues and social networks). Getting more than a few hundred people to read it on Facebook costs a lot of money. Moreover, only 1% of the people who click on an article will actually read it in its entirety, which highlights the real constraint. The issue is not the quantity of content being produced but rather how much of it is actually being consumed. Even if there are thousands of articles on a particular topic, the likelihood of them being widely read remains low. There is little evidence to suggest that this trend will change significantly.

Also, LLMs might also help trustworthy institutions. They might not write important pieces of information by ChatGPT, but journalists might ask questions to LLMs to help them do other parts of their jobs, instead of writing the final piece.

2. Second, AI floods the internet with false information and generate noise

AI could help generate an overwhelming amount of low-quality or misleading content, making it difficult for people to distinguish truth from falsehood. This strategy is already confusing people enough to make them distrust the entire information ecosystem. The primary concern is not necessarily that people will be persuaded by specific falsehoods, but that the sheer volume of misinformation will increase the overall noise in the information environment. This leads to a noisy internet filled with content that appears credible, making people sceptical of all information and leading to a general disinterest in checking facts or forming strong opinions.

Historically, some governments have employed similar strategies to control their populations by flooding the information space with noise and confusion. Such strategy prevents citizens from trusting any source of information, thereby disengaging them from public discourse. An example is the current scepticism around news regarding the Russian invasion of Ukraine, where propaganda from multiple sides, including through the use of deepfakes (see Box 5 "The case of deepfakes"), has led to a decrease in public efforts to understand the situation. **The spread of misinformation by official sources, such as governments, academics, or major newspapers, poses a significant risk.** Such

³ <https://80000hours.org/podcast/episodes/hugo-mercier-misinformation-mass-persuasion/>

instances of "official misinformation" are particularly harmful as they carry more weight and have a wider reach. It is crucial to address this major issue to maintain public trust in authoritative sources. The prevalence of conspiracy theories is often linked to the level of corruption and mistrust in institutions, highlighting the importance of maintaining transparency and accountability. Moreover, the long-term impact of AI-generated content is uncertain, especially for future generations who will grow up in a world saturated with such content. Future generations may find it harder to distinguish between real and AI-generated information, unlike those with more established views of the world. This could lead to increased scepticism and reduced trust in information sources over time.

The case of deepfakes

Deepfakes – that is, videos that are manipulated using artificial intelligence to appear as though someone is saying or doing something they did not – constitute a more specific challenge. Some studies (e.g., Dobber et al., 2021) suggest that they can significantly influence political attitudes, especially when they are micro-targeted to specific demographic groups. Deepfakes would thus be a powerful mode of disinformation, along with other forms such as false news stories or trolling on social media platforms. For example, a deepfake video discrediting a political candidate can negatively affect people's attitudes towards both the politician and their associated party. Yet, other studies show that deepfakes are more effective when they are shown to demographic groups that are already personally interested in their content. Strong supporters of a candidate will disregard a deepfake video discrediting their candidate, due to their existing beliefs and loyalties.

While deepfakes are in some ways groundbreaking, they are a continuation of manipulation tactics that have existed for some time, including rhetoric, propaganda, and deceptive presentation of facts (Etienne, 2021). The narrative that deepfakes pose an unprecedented threat to information trustworthiness is not as solid as it seems. Deepfake technology is developing fast, but it is neither the first nor the most powerful tool to manipulate information. Deepfakes themselves are not the cause of a loss of trust among the public: distrust in political representatives and institutions predate this technology.

Instead of deepfakes contributing to a post-trust era, they might instead intensify existing scepticism or the erosion of trust, leveraging generalised distrust that already exists in society. Deepfakes could actually aid in the transition from instrumental rationality to social rationality by fostering a critical approach to information consumption and trust-building in the digital age. Just as societies learned to question the authenticity of photographs, the presence of deepfakes may teach people to develop a more critical and informed approach to digital content, encouraging the search for trustworthy sources of information.

The case of deepfake videos is revealing in that it shows the point at which belief in the truth of the information conveyed can actually be a problem. If someone cares about a particular issue (because there is a lot at stake for them), they will be more cautious.

Box 1 – The case of deepfakes

Yet, despite the proliferation of low-quality content, many people still rely on curated information from trusted sources. The credibility of the source remains a key factor in determining the reliability of information (Druckman, 2022). If established and trusted sources, such as reputable newspapers or well-regarded colleagues, continue to maintain their standards, the overall impact of AI-generated misinformation may be mitigated. The role of these curators is crucial in ensuring that information

remains trustworthy, even in the midst of a flood of junk content. There are also good reasons to think that the demand for truthful information will ensure the persistence of reliable sources. As long as there is a demand for accuracy, institutions will likely continue to provide truthful content, supported by the need to maintain their reputation. Competition among multiple sources of information can help ensure that false information is called out and corrected, maintaining the integrity of the information ecosystem. The effectiveness of misinformation can therefore be countered if reliable institutions continue to function and maintain public trust. In authoritarian regimes, where the government can control and flood the information space, credible private actors are often suppressed, making it easier to mislead the public. But in democratic societies with multiple sources of reliable information, it is more challenging for misinformation to take root extensively.

In conclusion, while there are legitimate concerns that AI will undermine our ability to have rational discussions, there are also reasons to believe that the risk may not be as dramatic. Overall, while the proliferation of AI-generated content poses significant challenges to information quality, the role of trusted sources and institutions remains central to mitigating its impact. The demand for truth and mechanisms to ensure accountability and reliability in the dissemination of information are critical to maintaining a trustworthy information environment.

Trust in the ethical use of personal data

There are a number of concepts related to personal data which are not equivalent, from intimacy to privacy and personal data per se (see Box 6 “The evolution of the notion of privacy”). What should really be protected? Recommendations can hardly be limited to a simple and unique claim for universal protection, which would apply to all private information, irrespective of its nature and the context in which it is used. Violations of intimacy must obviously be condemned, but what about private life, understood as the totality of ordinary daily activities?

The evolution of the notion of privacy

The notion of privacy is not universal and has evolved over time. Its history traces a complex evolution from ancient Greece to the 21st century. In ancient Greece, the distinction between private and public spaces shaped society, with the collapse of democratic institutions marking the loss of the complementary functions of these spaces. The Middle Ages saw the emergence of networks of solidarity and shared resources, challenging the concept of private and public realms. The modern age, particularly in England and France during the Revolution, introduced liberties that protected citizens from public interference in personal affairs. The 20th century witnessed totalitarian regimes aspiring to control individuals' private spheres, leading to the inclusion of privacy protection in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948. Authoritarian states exploited personal data to maintain their hold over those they dominate, and totalitarian states exploited it even more.⁴ The 21st century now presents new challenges. Web platforms mine vast amounts of information about the

⁴ For Hannah Arendt, the opening of the private sphere to the public gaze - and thus, in a sense, its disappearance as a private sphere - leads to a shrinking of the common sphere, and thus of the political sphere (Biesta, 2023). The more private communities and solidarity networks provide for individuals, the less important the public sphere becomes, because decisions are taken elsewhere, and the space for politics is consequently reduced. The more the private sphere enters the public sphere, the more paralysed the discussion of public affairs inevitably becomes.

world, collecting individual data for profit and challenging the traditional roles of states in security, education and health.

Box 2 – The evolution of the notion of privacy

How user data are used by online platforms is also hard to assess. Even data that is in principle public (such as the number of tweets for a keyword) is difficult to access, and much of it is not available at all. TikTok has launched its own API⁵ to analyse the activity of the platform's users, but it actually provides very little data. Moreover, there is no guarantee that what the platforms share is actually up to date. In any case, most of the rules of the algorithm are derived from AI models trained on large amounts of behavioural data. The system is emergent and only marginally dependent on rules as explicit as "If the post is toxic, then make it more visible".

Communities of researchers – such as AI Forensics' TikTok Global Observatory⁶ – get around the issue by running simulations. Bouchaud, Chavalarias & Panahi (2023) showed that Twitter's "For You" recommendation feed contained 50% more toxic messages than the feed of accounts that the user followed. But each new version of the applications makes it more difficult for researchers to capture what lies underneath social media platforms' activity. The DSA could facilitate this approach by allowing researchers to get access to protected data (Article 40). However, such access will need to be highly controlled, and raise additional questions related, e.g., to the process of authorising access and assessing the quality of the associated research. Another solution for researchers is to rely on data donation, by asking participants recruited for this purpose to install extensions on their computers to collect their data. This is a time-consuming and cumbersome process, but which remains an efficient way of obtaining reliable information. Be that as it may, governments must be able to take more action, and propose rules that can actually be applied.

Regarding data processing, international regulations such as GDPR provides a framework for data exploitation in Europe, including by limiting the collection of information to what is strictly necessary, securing access to databases, destroying data after a certain period of time, encouraging anonymisation, and so on. Regarding recommendation systems, a law was passed in France in July 2023 to introduce the digital age of majority: under the age of 15, parental consent is required for young people to access social networks. The same year, the European Digital Service Act was passed to regulate the activities of platforms and provide greater protection for users. Platforms now have to assess the risks induced by their recommendation systems and mitigate them. They have to explain in the Terms and Conditions of use, the parameters used and the options that are available for changing them. They also have to offer the possibility of an alternative news feed (although this may remain an option that the user must activate). The DSA also requires platforms to provide transparency about advertisements, so that users know that they are receiving an ad, on whose behalf it is being sent, and why the advertisement has been selected for them.

Then again, implementing these practices must benefit the user first, and not only protect against legal risks. **Regulation has to be useful and desirable: people should know why a given regulation has been decided, and why it is better for the majority of users.** Ideally, platforms should allow third parties to provide recommendation systems that would allow users to select algorithms that suit

⁵ API stands for Application Programming Interface, which is a set of functions, procedures, methods or classes used by computer programs to request services from the operating system, software libraries or any other service providers running on the computer (source: Wikipedia.com)

⁶ <https://tkgo.aiforensics.org/>

them, providing them with interesting information while at the same time, making that choice genuinely informed.

This development reflects an ongoing struggle between the protection of privacy and the risk of intrusion by states and by corporations. As the case of China illustrates, the risk of totalitarian states remains, underlining the relevance of privacy protections in the face of changing societal and technological landscapes. Furthermore, the disclosure of personal information grants real power over individuals. Maintaining a representative democracy requires that privacy be protected, so that individuals can freely express their opinions and contribute to public debate, without having to bow to central control. Personal security also requires that individuals are not vulnerable to malicious private actors and hackers.

That said, the exploitation of personal data by governments does not necessarily lead to an abuse of power. The protection of personal data as a universal requirement does not refer to the same thing depending on whether the data is private, intimate, anonymous or not, whether it is held by a government or by a private company, and so on. A state can use health information about its population to protect it from a pandemic, as was the case during the Covid crisis.⁷ Governments also use large quantities of personal data for the public good, in the exercise of their duty to protect citizens, which is obviously a good thing, provided that they do not take advantage of it to use it for coercion (governments can also make use of big data and AI for much more dubious purposes, such as determining an individual's political orientation (Kosinski, 2021; Rasmussen et al., 2023). Democratic safeguards are therefore needed to guarantee the trustworthiness of our institutions. **Citizens must weigh up the risks of sharing their personal data against the benefits, while guaranteeing the transparency and reliability of our institutions.** Hence the importance of transparency of intent and alignment between the goals of the trustor and the trustee.

Consequences of algorithms for the quality of public deliberation

Information shared on social media, with or without malicious intent, can play a major role in altering the quality of public debate. Not necessarily because people incorporate false information into their belief system, but because it may contribute to creating a climate of mistrust in institutions. The massive use by social networks of algorithms, designed to optimise user engagement, appears to be amplifying this phenomenon. How access to quality information has been undermined by the massive use of AI and algorithms in digital media, and how these shape individuals' online behaviours, reasoning faculties and opinions, remains extremely important questions, whose answers are not quite settled yet.

We are wired to favour socially congruent and emotionally relevant information

Evolution has shaped our minds to prioritise loyalty to our groups and develop certain biases favouring our community, which are likely present across all groups. Modern politics vividly demonstrates how coalitions can provoke strong biases. Algorithms understand this well, exploiting our cognitive tendencies to promote the most divisive content (Clark et al., 2019). They contribute to distorting the logic of informational exchanges on the Internet by encouraging the polarisation of exchanges, because the aim of social media platforms is to increase user engagement.

⁷ See for example, Taiwan's successful handling of the Covidien crisis. <https://fsi.stanford.edu/news/how-taiwan-used-big-data-transparency-central-command-protect-its-people-coronavirus>

The truthfulness of information is less relevant when the paramount aspect lies in the ability of the induced emotion to be justified and shared among individuals (Schaffner & Luks, 2018). Substantial experimental evidence corroborates the widespread phenomenon of emotional transmission across social networks (Kramer et al., 2014; Martel et al., 2024). Emotions serve as influential drivers for dissemination within social media spaces, particularly when expressing negative sentiments or moral emotions (Brady et al., 2017).

Moreover, attitudinal disagreements are often coupled with mistrust and contempt (reflected by the notion of affective – as opposed to attitudinal – polarisation) and these can be fed by moral and emotional content (Van Bavel & Pereira, 2018). Groups with different interests within polarities can also converge and fuel a movement of global polarisation (Benkler et al., 2018).

Psychological mechanisms

If exchanges on social networks often lack politeness, it is also because of the possibility of exchanging with anonymous, depersonalised strangers. This experience, unique to the Internet age (Bor & Petersen, 2022), reduces our sense of personal responsibility and empathy towards interlocutors whom we no longer see as individuals but as interchangeable members of political 'tribes' (Combs et al., 2023).

Mathematician David Chavalarias (2023) points to an insidious danger directly linked to attentional capture, namely the tendency of networks to exacerbate the small differences and micro-conflicts. Positions are not necessarily more radical, but hostility between different positions is said to have increased. Discourses pointing to societal threats enjoy a considerable competitive advantage in the market of ideas and conversations, because of their appeal to our minds (Acerbi, 2019a; Blaine & Boyer, 2018; Boyer & Parren, 2015).

Recent analyses also point out that **social networks – and newspapers as well – function less as a mirror than as a distorting prism for the diversity of opinions in society**. Social networks seem to contribute to increasing political hostility and radicalism because people are exposed to caricatural and aggressive versions of opposing political positions, which are a source of irritation. The majority of users, who are more moderate, are reluctant to engage in political discussions that rarely reward good faith. In fact, outraged and potentially offending political posts are often made by people who are more determined to express their views and who are more radical than the average – whether they are signalling their commitment, expressing their anger or promoting their views. Even though they represent a relatively small proportion of the written output on the networks, these posts are promoted by algorithms programmed to highlight content capable of attracting attention and triggering responses, of which divisive messages are a good example (Chavalarias, 2023).

Most of our virtual connections do not develop into 'echo chamber', isolating us within entirely homogeneous pools of political ideas. **The diversity of opinions with which we are confronted online is frequently greater than that of our friendships**. This exposure to ideological alterity is desirable, in theory, as it should enable us to discover the blind spots in our political knowledge and convictions (Bakshy et al., 2015; De Francisci Morales et al., 2021; Guess et al., 2018), our common humanity⁸, and therefore make us both more humble and more respectful of each other. Unfortunately, the way in which most people express their political convictions rather lacks both nuance and pedagogy. It

⁸ See the contact hypothesis: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Contact_hypothesis

tends to reduce opposing positions to caricatures and seeks less to persuade the other side than to rally those who already agree with you, or to make political friends (Grubbs et al., 2019).

A series of experimental studies carried out on Twitter, as well as interviews with Democratic and Republican activists by sociologist Chris Bail and his colleagues (2018) show that repeated exposure to weak and mocking content produced by political enemies can paradoxically reinforce supporters in their pre-existing positions and identities (Törnberg, 2022), rather than bringing them intellectually and emotionally closer to each other.

The role of algorithms

Social networks allow content to be distributed identically to millions of people – unlike verbal communication, where distortions are inevitable (Marie et al., 2020). As such, they can misinform or antagonise millions of people at very little cost. This is true whether the false or toxic information is intentionally created to generate clicks, or whether it is the unintended result of the political biases of a given political group.

Understanding the intricate and often opaque nature of interactions between users and the algorithms that curate content on social media and other online platforms is crucial but challenging due to limited transparency and the dynamic nature of the algorithms (Lewandowsky et al., 2024). How social media algorithms work remains very opaque, but timelines will certainly favour content that has been the subject of higher engagement. An obvious consequence is that posts prompting for an immediate reaction will climb to the top of the newsfeed. Pictures of a cat doing a funny face will have no real consequences, but the same is true for controversial political opinions, which will cause many comments, or for sensational stories that will generate more interest and will be “liked” more.

Recent research conducted by Rathje, Van Bavel & van der Linden (2021), analysing 2.7 million posts on Facebook and Twitter, underscores the **strong predictive nature of content targeting out-groups in driving engagement across social media platforms**. The quality of public debate thus seems to be threatened by increased polarisation: recommendation engines, with the aim of keeping users for as long as possible, come up with increasingly polarising content. Such dynamics can even lead to violent behaviours, as shown by the role of social media in organising the storming of the U.S. Capitol on January 6, 2021.

A model proposed by Santos, Lelkes and Levin (2021) shows how the strength of social influence affects opinion dynamics, by stressing the role of link recommendation algorithms commonly used in online social networks in the creation of ties and opinion polarisation. Algorithms tend to suggest new connections between users with a high number of common acquaintances, which can promote structural similarity and the formation of isolated, like-minded communities. In this context, even moderate opinions can contribute significantly to opinion polarisation. Other empirical data suggests that link recommendation algorithms do indeed change the rewiring pattern of social networks.

In recent years, online platforms have been showing increased recognition of the issues surrounding the algorithms used to maximise user engagement, and have committed to working on solutions to the problem of the problematic use of social media among the youth. For instance, in 2022, Instagram introduced a feature called “take a break”, as another measure to address user engagement and well-being, and in 2023 TikTok introduced a 60-minute time restriction for users under 18, which requires the user to enter a password to continue. Disabling push notifications has been made easier, and

notifications are now deactivated after 9pm for users aged 13-15, and after 10pm for those aged 16-17.

Individual vs. societal consequences

The consequences of information are not the same at the individual and societal levels. Upholding distorted depictions on certain topics, especially those with significant political and social ramifications, can result in profound effects, impacting areas such as health and politics. The success of political endeavours relies on their adherence to a truthful representation of reality. The collective understanding of this representation holds significant consequences when influencing the outcomes of decisions made by society as a whole. Democracy indeed requires a common base of knowledge among citizens to function optimally, which includes trust in electoral processes and evidence to inform policy debates (Lewandowsky et al., 2023).

Research shows that widespread disinformation campaigns are eroding the shared knowledge that democracy depends on, thereby undermining democratic institutions and processes (Lewandowsky et al., 2023). Not because people believe in this false information, but because they have less trust in the benevolence of media institutions. Even when the epistemic commitment to misconceptions about the world is not very strong and may only be a means of justifying pre-existing intuitions, individual attitudes can be harmful when they become dominant in the public sphere. Once a narrative enters public discourse, it has the potential to evolve into a norm that shapes the perception of societal issues. Consequently, modes of thinking that prioritise coalition-building over collaboration and truth-seeking may dominate more moderated forms of discourse. Returning to a peaceful debate is then very difficult, as people are even less interested in hearing contradictory views. Positions defended for social or identity-related reasons can in turn lead to the undermining of the common ground on which decisions taken at societal level are based. If this common ground is not clearly identified and shared by all, the public debate becomes distracted from the real issues facing society.

This polarisation impedes collective decision-making, as citizens are less inclined to engage with opposing perspectives or to work together to achieve common goals. In terms of social attitudes, polarisation undermines the foundations of constructive social debate, fostering intolerance and hostility rather than open and respectful dialogue. As a result, it diminishes the ability to find consensus or compromise, essential elements of a functioning democratic process. If citizens are to remain genuine actors involved in collective decision-making, the issue of truthfulness in the exchange of information, including on the internet, should become an individual priority. Users must be given the means to protect themselves against polarising mindsets when navigating the internet.

How AI could foster public deliberation

Historically, technologies that enhance information transmission tend to benefit society more than they harm it. For instance, **AI could automatically suggest fact-checking annotations for social media posts**, improving the overall quality of information.

Future AI developments, particularly large language models (LLMs), hold the potential to significantly improve our ability to ascertain truth and enhance the quality of online and real-life discussions. One idea is to have individualised fact-checking or reasoning checks alongside every social media post on controversial political topics. These checks could identify logical inconsistencies or contradictions with established facts, such as those found on Wikipedia. While not mandatory, social networks could incentivise the use of such systems by boosting posts that opt in for these verifications. For instance,

LLMs could also be employed to identify and flag misleading AI-generated accounts, reducing their exposure or facilitating their removal. This proactive measure leverages AI to maintain the integrity of online discourse by addressing the very tactics used to spread misinformation. An efficient, automatic fact-checking mechanism on platforms like X could drastically improve the informational environment.

Another approach involves deploying information bots to counteract misinformation bots on social media. There could be **bots designed to disseminate accurate information and engage in polite, constructive dialogue**. By being just as numerous and prolific as misinformation bots, these information bots could attract followers who value truthful content, effectively balancing the informational environment.

However, this might also lead to a segregation where individuals not interested in accurate information might migrate to other platforms. This segregation raises questions about the overall benefit but highlights the feasibility of creating more reliable social networks.

One concern is the democratisation of engaging content creation. Currently, well-resourced institutions can produce more engaging content due to higher production costs. If creating compelling content becomes cheaper and more accessible, smaller groups with fewer resources could also compete for attention. This could potentially level the playing field, but it could also make it easier for misleading information to spread if smaller, less trustworthy groups use these tools.

While this possibility exists, it is not inherently negative. Even reputable sources can occasionally misreport or overlook important issues. Therefore, smaller or local outlets might use advanced AI tools to produce compelling stories on topics that larger outlets miss. Nonetheless, people will eventually discern misleading content, especially if it is exaggerated or false, as they tend to seek feedback and verify information over time.

On the use of AI by citizens in knowledge-based activities

AI and social fairness

In the course of their evolution, humans have organised themselves in cooperative settings, and it was crucial to share cooperation benefits in a mutually advantageous manner (Baumard, 2011). Those who were too individualistic risked losing partners, while those taking less than their share risked exploitation by partners receiving more than they contributed. This competition resulted in the evolution of a sense of fairness, a cognitive adaptation aiming to equally share cooperation benefits. Evolution favoured fairness because impartial individuals were chosen more often as cooperation partners. Morality may therefore have evolved as an adaptation to an environment marked by competitive dynamics among individuals seeking selection and recruitment in mutually advantageous cooperative interactions (Baumard et al., 2013). **Being fair and reliable made individuals attractive collaborators, leading to the widespread acceptance of fairness in groups.** Thus, people have a natural sense of what is right in distributing benefits, similar to making mutually beneficial agreements. Such behaviour often follows a pattern like social contracts, even in short-term interactions.

The issue of equity, defined as rewarding according to contribution, is a primary concern in the context of AI. In particular, equity is a key component of human fairness, as established in both philosophical

discourse and scientific inquiry (Debove et al., 2017). Philosophers have long underscored the importance of the notion that greater effort warrants greater benefits. Psychological research, particularly on distributive justice and equity theory, provides substantial empirical backing for the importance of merit-based rewards (Homans, 1958). A consistent finding is that receiving more or less than one deserves results in distress, prompting efforts to restore equity by adjusting one's contribution (Skitka & Wisneski, 2013). Preferences for income distributions reflecting strong work-salary correlations, greater rewards for more valuable contributions, and overall meritocratic distributions are evident in both micro- and macro-justice contexts (Baumard et al., 2013). This body of literature serves as a valuable foundation for examining the implications of tools like ChatGPT in diverse social contexts, such as education and work.

The adoption of AI-based tools can be perceived as problematic because it creates more occasions of potential inequality and dishonesty, eroding trust between group members who expect equal treatment for all. In academic contexts, the deployment of AI-tools such as ChatGPT raises concerns related to bias and fairness, as well as plagiarism. For instance, according to Reich (2022), AI's ability to generate high-quality essays may erode academic integrity. As AI technologies become easily accessible and increasingly difficult to detect, the potential for students to misuse these tools to cheat on assignments increases.

On the other hand, the use of AI tools like ChatGPT should not necessarily be seen as cheating or plagiarism. They may involve a process of analysis and evaluation by the student, which can be considered as work in its own right. What, then, are the conditions under which these tools can be used with equanimity, so that they are not perceived as potentially leading to a situation that would be perceived as unfair?

To answer this question, research into students' perceptions of what constitutes cheating in the academic context, and the motivations behind it, is quite relevant. For example, in a study by Beasley (2014), students reported that increased awareness of what constitutes cheating and academic dishonesty might have prevented their actions (e.g., through explicit guidelines during exams and assignments; clearer instructions from their professors, etc.). Many students rationalise their cheating by blaming professors, accusing them of failing to emphasise academic integrity or not creating a learning environment that supports honesty. Noteworthy, the use of AI in academic context creates a vacuum that is seen as an opportunity for some, and as an unfair advantage for others.

Broadly changing academic conduct policies to classify AI as a source of plagiarism would be a hasty decision and would be tantamount to throwing the baby out with the bathwater. Both students and teachers should develop an 'AI culture', which includes being aware of AI's pervasiveness, gaining the ability to use it, recognising that everyone can use it, and applying critical thinking to the content produced by AI. Rather than prohibiting AI tools in academia, it could be more beneficial to educate students about AI, its usage, and ethical implications. But whether this means preventing the use of AI-tools in certain test conditions, or making use of them by adapting what is asked of students, in the end, it is always a question of reassuring the institution's ability to sanction students fairly.

The valuation of human productions and the threat of AI

It may seem pointless to spend a lot of effort doing what a machine can do in a few minutes. The purpose of such effort is more obvious when it comes to developing a particular skill. In this case, the value lies in the intellectual effort required to achieve that goal. People can be replaced for a task they

don't want to do themselves, but personal effort is key to progress. Yet certain skills may seem outdated, such as manual arithmetic in the age of calculators. While basic manual calculation skills are still relevant, it makes more sense to focus on learning how to use these machines for advanced mathematical applications.

The case of cover letters is one of many examples. Knowing how to write the first draft of a cover letter using a tool such as ChatGPT can be just as useful as writing one from scratch. The ability to write a cover letter independently seems to have lost some of its importance. A large proportion of writing tasks in general are moving towards activities such as editing, proofreading and rewriting. Moreover, the increasing power of linguistic models is likely to accelerate this transformation. As a result, our approach to writing is likely to undergo a radical change.

With the advent of AI, the question of what is important to value as skills and talents is being raised more than ever. **Research on how people evaluate the value of productions (made by humans or by AI), and art in particular, provides an interesting insight, highlighting what is actually valued.**

For instance, Magni, Park & Chao (2024) showed that people evaluate creativity differently based on whether artefacts are thought to be produced by either AI or humans. They found that there is a context-dependent bias against AI in creative production. Specifically, the bias against AI creative artefacts manifested in some contexts (like paintings) but not others (like advertisement posters and business ideas). A key finding was that AI is perceived to require less effort than humans in the production of creative outputs, and this perception mediates the relationship between the producer's identity and the creativity attributed to the production. Thus, **the perception of effort is an important mediator in the evaluation of creative products.** A folk psychology approach provides a framework for understanding how the identity of the producer affects people's evaluations of creative work: people may perceive artificial agents as lacking emotional and intentional capabilities, which are considered important in creative processes.

Another study (although not about artificial intelligence) highlights the role of effort in evaluating artistic production. Kruger et al. (2004) tested the hypothesis that people used the effort invested in the creation of a product as a heuristic, or mental shortcut, for judging its quality. The idea was that this heuristic is used because direct assessment of quality is often difficult. By manipulating the reported effort put into the creation of various artefacts (like poems, paintings, and suits of armour) and keeping the actual quality constant, the researchers sought to demonstrate that judgments of quality could be swayed erroneously by the perceived effort alone, potentially leading to misjudgement. They made a distinction between self-generated effort, which is associated with dissonance theory, and other-generated effort. The effort heuristic discussed in this paper refers to the judgments about efforts made by others, not by oneself. The authors suggest that the reliance on the effort heuristic is stronger in situations where the quality of the object being evaluated is ambiguous. They argue that in the case of objects like art, where quality is not readily apparent and can be subjective, the reported effort put into the object's creation becomes a default indicator of quality. The effort heuristic is widely used among different types of individuals (including self-identified experts) and across domains, indicative of its general appeal as a basis for judgement. So, while effort can indeed be a generally reliable indicator of quality, there are instances where it may fail to accurately reflect the true value of a work, leading to incorrect judgments of quality.

Other studies show that humans tend to prefer artworks labelled as human-created over those labelled as AI-created (Bellaiche et al., 2023). This observed preference is consistent across several judgement criteria, such as Liking, Beauty, Profundity, and Worth. Labels such as "Human-created" or "AI-created" can heavily influence individuals' enjoyment, trust, and valuation of the artworks, regardless of the actual creator. Interestingly, higher perceived effort leads to a greater appreciation when labelled as "human-created." Similar findings were observed in the music domain. There seems to exist an "AI composer bias" where listeners' enjoyment and quality ratings of music are influenced by their knowledge or beliefs about the composer's identity (Shank et al., 2023). People like music less and judge it as lower in quality if they believe it was composed by an AI compared to believing it was composed by a human. Even with no actual difference in the music itself, the perceived identity of the composer can significantly affect listeners' aesthetic judgments.

Intentionality (i.e. the intention of the author of an artwork) seems to be a fundamental ingredient in the evaluation of the quality of an artistic production. As art is not only a physical stimulus, but also a means of human expression and communication, the importance attached to the author's true intentionality can outweigh aesthetic assessment. Creation indeed involves conceiving a mental concept for the artefact (by an author) and then physically manufacturing it (by an instrument), typically within a single individual. The concept of Mental Primacy (Judge et al., 2020) emphasises that the generation of ideas (mental labour) is valued more than the execution of those ideas through physical labour, in Western societies. Intellectual Property laws reflect this by protecting an author's mental concepts, sometimes even before their physical realisation. Is it grounded in the belief that mental and physical processes complement each other in the creation process, producing a more valuable artefact. This notion implies that a material artefact's true value is released when an idea is embodied through skilful and effortful physical work. Both the mental and physical essences of makers are transmitted to the material artefact. This influences how artefacts are valued and perceived in terms of authenticity, ownership, and connection to the creator. Folk theories of artefact creation significantly impact human-artefact relations, affecting how people evaluate different types of artefacts and their makers. Such theories can shape cultural materials and influence societal views on production and consumption. Other cultures have different preconceptions about value and authenticity (see for instance Coleman (2001), who shows that paintings considered inauthentic from a Western perspective may be authentic within Aboriginal contexts).

The perceived value of an artwork is heavily influenced by whether an object is categorised as art, which can be shaped by the creator's intent, and not just by its functional use (Newman & Bloom, 2012). People's judgements about the value of art are influenced by the intentions of the original maker to make the object a work of art or artefact. This ties in with the notion that artistic achievement is inherently linked to the artist's intention and the unique process of creation.

In the economic sphere, consumers have a special appreciation for handmade products, viewing them as more attractive compared to machine-made products. This perceived value is known as the "handmade effect." One reason for the handmade effect may be that consumers believe handmade products are imbued with love (Fuchs et al., 2015). This belief would come from the perception that artisans invest personal care and affection into the production process. Despite rapid technological advancement in manufacturing, human craftsmanship is unlikely to become obsolete. Handmade products fulfil a consumer desire for goods that embody human attributes like love and care, which cannot be replicated by machines. Skills associated with hand making products are thus likely to remain valuable in the labour market due to consumer preferences for goods made with human touch.

This is an interesting parallel to be drawn with the case of AI-generated content: one can hardly imagine that human creation will lose its value anytime soon. The question is rather to understand how people attribute value to human creation.

Rethinking with AI our relationship with the world and with others

Another effect of AI on our relationship with others comes from the opacity of AI-based systems, and the absence of any possibility of real interaction. Because such systems lack a theory of mind, they preclude the possibility of joint attention—a fundamental aspect of human communication and understanding. Indeed, attention is not merely a mechanism for filtering incoming information and stimuli. It enables individuals to organise their interactions with others – see, for example, Michael Tomasello's work on shared intentionality (Tomasello et al., 2005). This process is part of what is known as theory of mind, a highly influential paradigm in cognitive science for understanding human interaction. It assumes that humans have developed a specialised cognitive equipment that enables them to represent the mental states of others, i.e. their intentions, volitions, desires and beliefs. Theory of mind is a component of social cognition, enabling us to communicate and interact with others.

Preserving we-mode interactions

Another approach to the social nature of attention is the “we-mode” (Gallotti & Frith, 2013). Typical examples of we-mode are the experience of watching a live soccer match or following a classroom lecture. In these moments, participants experience a shared flow of information with other members of their group. The hypothesis of Shteynberg et al. (2020) is that **shared attention increases the allocation of cognitive resources dedicated to information**, which is the object of attention of the social group. Sandberg suggests that when people believe they are acquiring information with members of their group (information that is a priori likely to be encountered in subsequent social interactions), it becomes more psychologically salient. From an evolutionary point of view, better processing of such information would increase the individual's readiness for group coordination and collective action. This can be linked with Gergely and Csibra's Natural Pedagogy theory (2009), which posits that human beings are uniquely equipped to engage in communicative interactions that facilitate learning and knowledge transfer. People process information differently depending on whether it is recognised as shared knowledge. When information is perceived as shared, individuals engage more deeply, considering the intentions and perspectives of others. In contrast, information not recognised as shared is processed more superficially, without the same level of social and contextual integration. These nuanced human capabilities highlight the significant gap between human and AI communicative interactions.

As part of a research project on future scenarios in June 2020, Stefania Broadbent conducted in-depth interviews with students in Milan, during the lockdown of Covid 19 (Broadbent et al., 2024). The main finding was that, when students complained of not being able to concentrate during remote lectures, the reason was not just a lack of ability to focus. It was mainly that there was no one present with whom they could share their attention. The distraction was due to environmental factors, but also to a lack of engagement. A live lecture is a shared experience, offering a common focus that enhances attention and concentration. It offers content that is shared both cognitively and socially, a common foundation on which to build various forms of coordination, collaboration and solidarity.

The case of human-machine interactions

The systematic integration of AI into many applications raises major questions for joint attention. When using ChatGPT for instance, users spend a considerable amount of time generating instructions to achieve the required result, via the development of prompts. A significant part of this time is spent trying to guess how the system will respond and react. The impossibility to identify what the system knows are, and on what information its responses are based, makes it almost impossible to anticipate its responses, which often leads to accepting what is proposed in an uncritical way, or rejecting suggestions out of hand. For several years now, AI has been criticised for its lack of transparency, but this is often about the mechanisms underlying algorithmic decisions. The problem also lies in the cognitive nature of human-machine interaction. **The impossibility of anticipating and reading an artificial mind, without a theory of mind, reduces the possibility of cooperation, and confronts the human with the alternative of accepting or rejecting the solution proposed by the system.**

In our social interactions and epistemic practices, we rely on reputation mechanisms to judge the value of information (Origgi, 2018). How we should position ourselves with regard to information coming from such an opaque system is not straightforward. In the socio-ethnological sense, culture presupposes the awareness of fine-grained nuances of language, objects and social situations, and the ability to choose the right word or action. This implies the acquisition of a coherent set of automatisms enabling us to interact with certain particular dimensions of the environment, in a given situation. Developing a culture of attention means increasing each person's ability to make themselves accessible to many rich microworlds (Broadbent et al., 2024).

The problem with opaque algorithms is not that they generate biased representations, but that they impose worldviews

For many experts, the development and use of large language models in natural language processing is leading to significant risks for society, including the propagation of biases, perpetuation of harmful stereotypes, and the production of misleadingly fluent but potentially harmful content without accountability (Bender et al., 2021). While some algorithms are indeed biased, due to the data on which they have been trained, the overall prevalence of bias remains relatively limited (relative to the base frequency). Greater risks lie in the use of discriminating categories, and in unfounded reliance on AI tools, rather than in biases inherent in the algorithms themselves. The temptation to call for absolute transparency is strong, but one might in fact wonder to what extent is such transparency necessary, or even desirable. The question of how and to whom this transparency could be really useful is not trivial. There is in fact a certain incompatibility between clarity and understandability, because good explanations often require the use of intuitive but misleading representations. Rather than making absolute demands in terms of transparency, we need to consider the conditions for informed confidence on the part of users in AI-based systems. In other words, transparency should not be called for its own sake, but to allow for informed confidence.

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

[@kt4democracy.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/org/kt4democracy)

[KT4Democracy](https://www.linkedin.com/company/kt4democracy)

Funded by
the European Union